

Nitrogen release patterns of sulfur-coated urea in wetland rice

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The low agronomic efficiency of applied N fertilizer in wetland rice is of major concern to scientists and farmers in South and Southeast Asia. Nitrogen efficiency can be increased by applying modified urea materials. An example is sulfur-coated urea (SCU), which has been widely tested in wetland rice. International Network on Soil Fertility and Fertilizer Evaluation for Rice (INSFFER) trials conducted at the PAU farm have consistently shown that SCU application gives higher rice yields than other modified urea materials.

A field experiment to determine N release patterns of SCU in flooded soils was conducted during 1982 kharif on a sandy loam soil (Typic Ustochrepts: pH 8.5, EC 0.15 mmho/cm, 0.23% organic carbon, 0.04% total N, and 4.54 meq cation exchange capacity/100 g). A small nylon screen bag with 460 mg N as SCU (38.6% N) was placed between two layers of wet soil freshly collected from the lower layer of the experimental plots. The bags were placed 10 cm deep in the centers of 4 hills spaced at 15 × 20 cm, 5 days after 45-day-old PR1 06 seedlings were transplanted.

Bags from 4 hills were chosen at random and SCU granules were digested and analyzed for urea N at 1, 3, 6, 10, 25, 45, and 60 days after placement. The remaining wet soil mass was extracted with 2M KCl-PMA solution and the extract was analyzed for NH_4^+ -N and urea-N. Nontreated soil was also analyzed and results corrected for native soil KCl-extractable NH_4^+ -N.

Results showed that SCU granules released urea-N at a fairly even rate up to 60 days after placement. Three days after placement, 83% of urea-N remained in the SCU granules (Fig. 1). Six days after placement 70% urea-N remained. Dissolution rate was about 9% higher than its empirical 7-day dissolution rate of 21%. After 60 days of placement, 44% urea-N still remained.

1. Changes in urea-N remaining at deep placement sites after application of sulfur-coated urea (SCU) in a wetland soil. *Bottom:* 2. Changes in KCl-extractable NH_4^+ -N remaining at deep placement sites after application of sulfur-coated urea (SCU) in a wetland soil.

KCl-extractable NH_4^+ -N peaked at 21.5 mg N (4.7% of N placed) 6 days after placement. Maximum NH_4^+ -N did not exceed 10 mg N for the remaining period (Fig. 2). At 60 days, 45.5% total

N (urea-N + NH_4^+ -N) remained, suggesting that SCU granules were protected pools supplying N to the soil solution at an even rate.